

A STUDY OF MOTIVATIONAL DRIVERS FOR PROFESSIONAL GROWTH AMONG NURSES

Waqar Hussain Vighio¹, Tasawar Abbas², Muhammad Rafique³, Muhammad Yousuf Bhatti⁴, Sofia Noreen Aqeel⁵, Kazia Ishaq⁶, Irsa Abid Jawaid⁷, Fariha Aziz⁸, Syed Uzma Paiam Bukhari⁹

¹GBSN Scholar, Indus University of Health Sciences, Karachi Pakistan

²Charge Nurse Male, Faisalabad institute of Cardiology, Faisalabad, Punjab, Pakistan

³MSN, Assistant Professor, Department of Nursing Indus University of Health Sciences, Karachi, Sindh, Pakistan

⁴Assistant Professor, Department of Nursing Indus University of Health Sciences, Karachi, Sindh, Pakistan

⁵Senior Lecturer, Academics, MBA(MSHM), PRN BSN, RN, RM Indus University of Health Sciences (IUHS), Karachi, Sindh, Pakistan.

⁶Clinical Instructor, GBSN Scholar (DUHS) Indus University of Health Sciences (IUHS), Karachi, Sindh, Pakistan.

⁷GBSN, Dow University of Health Sciences, Karachi, Pakistan

⁸GBSN Scholar Indus University of Health Sciences, Karachi, Sindh. Pakistan

⁹Ph.D. Scholar, Assistant Professor, Indus University of Health Sciences, Karachi, Pakistan

⁹uzmazmat@gmail.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15056057>

Keywords

Article History

Received on 13 February 2025

Accepted on 13 March 2025

Published on 20 March 2025

Copyright @Author

Corresponding Author: *

Abstract

Nurses often experience a lack of recognition for their work, which diminishes their self-esteem and job happiness. The perception of nursing as a low-status profession by the general population exacerbates feelings of dissatisfaction and disempowerment. Underappreciation, unfavourable working conditions, and a lack of opportunity for professional development are the main connected issues that demotivate nurses in Pakistan to pursue their professional development. These factors foster an atmosphere in which nurses feel overworked and underappreciated, which can result in burnout and a desire to quit the field. The study aims to assess the Lack of motivation among staff nurses towards their personal and professional growth. A convenient sampling was employed. A semi-structured interview was conducted to collect rich data. The researcher performed interviews in compliance with the 2018 Ethical Guidelines of the British Educational Research Association (BERA) to uphold the ethical consideration of my research. Prior to performing the interview, informed consent was sought from the participant. Data is analysed through thematic analysis. the study came to five key conclusions that contribute to nurses demotivation which are inefficient workload distribution, salary concerns, Lack of emotional quotient of the leaders under whose supervision nurses work, moreover they are given minimal opportunities for their professional growth.

INTRODUCTION

A nurse is an individual who plays a vital role in providing quality care to members of society, whether they are healthy or sick (Jannah et al., 2024). The role

of nurses in providing healthcare facilities is pivotal, and they are the building blocks of healthcare systems, whether patient-related or system-wide, The role of

nurses is widely recognized across all categories of health professions, especially in OECD countries, whether they work in hospitals or communities (Akbari, 2024). Low pay and unfavorable working conditions are frequently cited by nurses as the main causes of their discontent and plans to leave the country in search of better chances (Naz et al., 2024). Only 32 percent of nurses report having access to programs for continuous education and job growth (Waris et al., 2024). Nursing workers experience irritation and a sense of stagnation when there are no formalized avenues for professional progress (Rahman et al., 2024). On the other hand, even while these elements lead to demotivation, some nurses express satisfaction with their work schedules and safety, suggesting that enhancements in particular areas could boost motivation and job satisfaction generally (Waris et al., 2024). It is necessary to introduce awards and achievements among staff nurses to help them perform their activities efficiently. The distribution of professional shields, certificates, acceptance of their progress, and motivation from higher authorities are factors that can increase staff nurses' efficiency in their work environment (Morrow, 2025). Studies have revealed that a comfortable working environment plays a significant role in the psychological and mental well-being of nurses (El-Gazar, 2025). Work pressure and family responsibilities are the biggest hindrances to nurses' professional growth (Wu, 2025). Nurses should be encouraged to participate in professional development opportunities, as these activities enable them to gain up-to-date knowledge and skills, which are essential for quality care (Fredericks, 2025). Seniors Nurses show more dissatisfaction towards their jobs and work environment than newly Qualified nurses (Nagel, 2025).

Role of Nurses in Hospital

To improve healthcare results, nurses in Pakistani hospitals play a variety of roles, including patient education, direct care, and effective communication. Nurses play a crucial role in the healthcare system, especially in high-stress situations like burn units and childbirth, when their abilities have a big influence on patient satisfaction and the standard of care. Informing patients about their medical issues and available treatments is a critical role of nurses. Although 64% of nurses need to improve their ability

to assess patients' educational requirements, 75% of nurses acknowledge the value of patient education, according to a survey conducted at PKLI Hospital (Mazzocca, 2025).

Better health outcomes and more patient satisfaction can result from effective patient education, underscoring the need for continual training in this field. Nurses working in burn units encounter particular difficulties, such as heavy workloads and psychological strain. Their experiences highlight the necessity of improved training and support networks to improve the quality of care (Limungi, 2025). Higher patient satisfaction is associated with nurses who have strong communication abilities. According to a study, the perceived quality of care and nurses' interpersonal communication skills are significantly correlated (Alshalawi, 2025). Effectively meeting patient needs requires ongoing professional development in communication.

Although nurses play a vital role, issues like understaffing and training continue to exist, which may make it more difficult for them to provide the best care possible. Pakistani healthcare services

Sustaining Quality Care in Pakistan Nursing Sector:

Understanding the motivational factors that affect nurses' performance and job satisfaction is essential to maintaining high-quality treatment in Pakistan's nursing industry. According to research, nurses are motivated by both internal and external influences, which is important for improving the standard of patient care. According to Waris et al. (2024), a sizable majority of nurses (68.9%) said they felt appreciated for their efforts, which raises motivation and morale. Professional development opportunities are essential; according to Waris et al. (2024), 72.5% of nurses say that career advancement is important for their motivation. High levels of satisfaction with workplace safety (81.9%) and work hours (93.3%) were observed, suggesting that a supportive atmosphere boosts motivation (Waris et al., 2024).

Despite favourable responses regarding recognition, only 32% of nurses had access to continuing education, and 21.7% of nurses were unhappy with their pay, indicating areas that require improvement (Waris et al., 2024). According to Li, B. (2025), there is a need for focused measures to increase interest in community health nursing because the poor adoption

of this area indicates a lack of desire among recent graduates. Although both internal and external factors have a big impact on motivation, it's important to take into account the larger picture of Pakistan's healthcare issues. To encourage a more motivated nursing workforce, systemic problems including low pay and few educational options may need to be addressed.

Problem Statement

According to Hameed (2024), nurses frequently feel that their contributions are not acknowledged, which lowers their sense of self and professional satisfaction. Feelings of discontent and disempowerment are made worse by the public's view of nursing as a low-status occupation (Hameed, 2024). With 70% of nurses reporting excessive workloads, job dissatisfaction is largely caused by high workloads and insufficient support (Naz et al., 2024). There is a dire need to find out the reasons of nurses demotivation .Hospital development is currently focused on patient safety. A patient safety culture is formed in large part by nurses, who make up the largest portion of hospital human resources and are frequently the ones that deal with patients. Poor quality and limited accessibility in health care have been linked to human resource crises in developing nations. Employee motivation is a significant aspect of this problem. Particularly, as nurses serve as a vital conduit between patients and health systems, their motivation should be taken into account.

Research Objective

To assess the factors of lack of motivation among staff nurses towards their personal and professional growth.

Research Question

What factors lead to lack of motivation among staff nurses ?

Theoretical Background

This study is supported by theory Maslow's Hierarchy of needs as the research topic is assessing the need of motivation among staff nurses towards personal and professional growth. Maslows's Hierarchy of needs is a theory of motivation given by Abraham Maslow in 1943. This theory states that human beings have different level of needs that must be filled one after the other according to the hierarchy. Maslow's hierarchy of needs proposes that lower-level needs must be fulfilled before higher-level needs can be addressed.

According to the Maslow's hierarchy of needs, physiological needs include needs that are essential for human survival such as food, water, shelter, and sleep (Maslow, 1943). According to the theory safety needs include needs related to security , stability and protection, such as employment, financial security and healthcare (Maslow, 1943). Needs related to the social relationships, such as friendship, intimacy, and family (Maslow, 1943). Needs related to the self-esteem, recognition, and respect such as achievements, status, and prestige (Maslow, 1943) Needs related to personal growth, creativity and fulfillment, such as realizing one's potential and persuring personal goals (Maslow, 1943).

Fig:1 Maslow’s Hierachary of Needs

Nurses Needs in Alignment with the Theory:

Physiological needs for staff nurses in context of Maslow Hierachary of needs include needs for Basics working condition, the environment in which staff nurses are working should be comfortable enough for staff nures to perform their tasks with efficiency, also include working hours, breaks during the working hours, and access to meal dursing shift. Salary needs must be fullfilled, to meet personal and family needs. Somehow physical environment factors, such as work load and staff shortage is chalenging for staff nurses to perform their tasks working in long shifts is also a cause of mental stress. Studies have revealed that a comfortable working environment plays a significant role in the psychological and mental well-being of nurses (Almeida, 2024) . In the context of malow theory safety needs include Job security, workplace environment, e.g. workplace violence. And policies to protoect the emotional and mental wellbeing of staff nurses. Work pressure and family responsibilities are the biggest hindrances to nurses’ professional growth (Abbas, 2022).

Social needs in the context of maslow theory include opportunities for the staff nurses to be in touch with the peers that builds a sence of comminucation at workplace, support from higher management and leaders (Patrician, 2022). Esteem needs include appriciation, recognition for their works, there

should be opportunities for nurses to lead show their expertise, carrer advancement goals, workplace support. It is necessary to introduce awards and achievements among staff nurses to help them perform their activities efficiently. The distribution of professional shields, certificates, acceptance of their progress, and motivation from higher authorities are factors that can increase staff nurses’ efficiency in their work environment (Sultana, 2024). Opportunities for staff nurses to show their skills and potentials , opportunities to get higher education, and trainig, and motivation towards towards personal and professional growth.

Nurses should be encouraged to participate in professional development opportunities, as these activities enable them to gain up-to-date knowledge and skills, which are essential for quality care (Mlambo, 2021).

Methodology:

Research Design:

A Qualitative ,case study design is used. Case study design is used to understand a single case very closely, to know issues of the large community with the same problems. In the definite period of the time (Hancock, 2021)

Population:

In the study, a Convenient sampling method was used. This sampling method is used to ease of accessibility and availability of the researcher and participant (Golzar, 2022). In this a participant participated in semi structured interview.

Data collection:

To collect the data participant is chosen, which is available in the working environment of the researcher with the ease. The participant is given a information and consent letter and also acknowledged about the confidentiality. The interview was conducted in the comfortable environment. In this study semi-structured interview was conducted. The participant was asked about working environment, opportunities for the staff nurses to study, basic fulfillment of their physiological, social and esteem needs. Semi structured interview gave flexibility in answers.

Ethical consideration:

To maintain the ethical consideration of my research, the researcher conducted interviews on accordance with British Educational Research Association's (BERA) 2018 Ethical Guidelines. An informed consents was obtained from the participant before

conducting interview. And assured that the confidentiality of the data will be maintained and will be accessible to authorized individuals. Participant is given any right to discontinue research at any phase with facing consequence.

Data Analysis:

Thematic Analysis : Thematic analysis is a qualitative research method used to examine and explain themes in qualitative data.

The data was read and read to become familiar with its content, the data was closely monitored to identify the themes. Inductive theme analysis method is used. After the close observation, five major findings of the study. All the themes are further divided into the section. The first theme is Physiological needs that is further divided into salary issues and Ineffective workload distribution. The second theme is Safety needs that is further divided into workplace violence. The third is social needs that is further divided into team work and behavior of supervisors. The fourth one is Esteem needs that is further divided into Acknowledgements and leadership opportunities and the fifth is Self Actualization that is further divided into the opportunities for growth and relevant career development programs.

Fig 2: Graphical Representation of Themes

Physiological Needs:

Maslow's hierarchy of requirements places physiological demands at the bottom. People require these things to physically survive (Buheji, 2023). Air, food, drink, clothing, warmth, sleep, shelter, and health are a few examples. Your body cannot operate correctly if you don't take care of these necessities. Existence, relatedness, and growth (ERG) are the three categories into which Clayton Alderfer divided Maslow's hierarchy of requirements (Arogundade, 2023). Psychological and safety needs are associated with existence, social and self-esteem requirements with relatedness, and self-actualization needs with growth. The ERG theory encourages pursuing multiple levels at once and does not impose a hierarchy on the sequence of needs fulfillment (Hsiao, 2022). Some employees are regressing, which manifests as their continued pursuit of lower-level requirements rather than higher-level ones. According to the thesis, managers must assist regressing workers in seeing the value of pursuing greater demands for their own development.

Salary Issues

Nurse undervaluation and pay are global issues rather than being restricted to any one nation or area (Thompson, 2022). In an effort to address the problems of underpayment and undervaluation, groups such as the ICN are aggressively promoting improved compensation and working conditions for nurses (Brubakk, 2024). Improved nurse outcomes—less burnout, job discontent, and desire to leave the job—have been found in hospitals with improved nurse staffing and work environments. However, wage impacts have not been taken into consideration in many studies, which could skew results (Manning, 2021).

p1: Salary and benefits are not enough to meet personal and family needs. Due to this majority of nurses apply for abroad nursing jobs.

This has been found that staff nurses are dissatisfied from their salary issues. This creates a sense of demotivation among nurses because despite of working in long shifts they don't get a deserving amount. So, they decide to leave country for abroad nursing. So, salary is the cause of demotivation among staff nurses.

Ineffective Workload:

One of the biggest issues facing the healthcare system is the excessive workload of hospital nurses (Ali, 2025). There are four primary reasons why nurses are dealing with more work than ever before: a decrease in patient length of stay, a shortage of nurses, a reduction in staffing and overtime, and an increase in demand for nurses (Akkuş, 2022). Hospitals are essential for delivering high-quality treatment, and the caliber of patient care is significantly impacted by the work of nurses. Among the difficulties faced by nurses are heavy workloads, abrupt changes in circumstances, and stress on an emotional level. There are not enough nurses to fulfill the demand as it stands, and as demand rises in the future and nursing schools are unable to meet the rising demand for education, the shortage is expected to worsen (Haroon, 2022). Those that stay on the job have more work to do when there is a scarcity of nurses.

P1: Sometimes not every time in case of public holidays, there is too much work load the main cause of work load is low staff ratio. Somehow work load and other factors leads to demotivation for higher studies.

It has been found that workload especially during public holidays and shortage of staff cause demotivation among staff nurses to pursue their dreams and receive higher education. Here are a few significant effects of a heavy nursing workload. According to research, patient safety is negatively impacted by a high nurse workload. Additionally, it has a detrimental impact on nurse job satisfaction, which in turn leads to high turnover and a nursing shortage. Nurses are expected to perform nonprofessional tasks like delivering and retrieving food trays, housekeeping, transporting patients, and ordering, coordinating, or performing ancillary services. These factors and expectations, in addition to the higher patient acuity, also contribute to the workload of nurses.

Safety needs

Ensuring a Secure Workplace Environment:

The workplace environment has an impact on employees' levels of creativity, motivation, engagement with coworkers, and loyalty to their jobs (Aldabbas, 2025). Some researchers claim that this aspect of relatedness to the employment environment has both positive and negative effects. Most working

conditions in emerging nations fall short of expectations. Regretfully, the majority of businesses do not make significant investments to maintain a suitable working environment since they view it as an unnecessary expense (Phuong Hong, 2024).

The tenets of human resource management (HRM) state that the organization's personnel are responsible for achieving better performance. As a result, workers are seen as an important resource for any company looking to boost performance (1). Prior to the last decades of the 20th century, performance was seen to be the outcome of a combination of talent and drive when given sufficient resources; as a result, inspiring others became a crucial component of most management. When human resources (HR) are utilized to their fullest potential, a company can achieve unbounded performance, efficiency, and production. Because each person has a unique working style, they might not all work in the same manner.

P1: Yes there are policies and resources present in organization to protect physical and emotional wellbeing. No violence form the team or supervisors but the attendants of patient are cause of violence in hospitals as adherence to guidelines is minimal.

It has been found there are enough policies to protect the physical and mental wellbeing, but the attendants of the patients create violence in hospital settings. So there is need to improve this practise and create a safe working environment to promote motivation among staff nurses towards personal and professional growth. A healthy work environment has two components: behavioral and physical. The aforementioned pertains to the elements that are connected to workers' capacity to maintain a physical connection to their places of employment. The workplace environment has a significant impact on how employees behave on an individual basis, even though office bearers' manners are impacted by the behavioral features of the environment. Therefore, the influence of workplace quality shapes employees' performance, efficiency, and incentive to work hard.

Social needs

Team work

In nursing, collaboration is crucial for more than just patient care (Olorunyomi, 2024). It significantly affects the culture of the workplace as well. A well-

functioning nursing team fosters an atmosphere where everyone is respected and heard. Better job satisfaction, less stress, and lower turnover rates are all facilitated by this. Good cooperation is acknowledged as one of the pillars of a healthy nursing workplace and is highlighted as a critical component of patient safety (Bukhari, 2024). Although the significance of job happiness in nursing has been established time and time again, the relationship between job satisfaction and nursing teamwork has only lately been discovered (Wiedermann, 2024).

P1: No opportunities to connect with the staff nurse. There are no activities that engage staff nurses with one another. They hospital management dont organize games or fun activities for nurses.

To ensure patient safety, nursing staff must collaborate because the current health care delivery system is intricate and evolving quickly. It has been found that no teamwork among staff nurses. No specific channels have been introduced for nurses to stay connected with one another. Apart from the work there should be fun activities for nurses to make them engaged in their working environment also the nurses stay motivated towards their growth

Low EQ of Leaders:

Nursing leaders with low emotional intelligence (EQ) may have a detrimental effect on nurse motivation, which may result in lower job satisfaction, higher burnout, and possibly worse patient outcomes (Amarneh, 2024). Low EQ leaders may find it difficult to comprehend and control both their own and their team members' emotions, which can cause strained relationships and poor communication (Bukhari S. U., 2024). This can result in a poisonous workplace where nurses feel ignored, underappreciated, and unsupported, which lowers morale and reduces job satisfaction. Increased stress and burnout among nurses can also result from leaders' lack of emotional intelligence and empathy (Juste, 2024).

P1: The behavior of management and supervisors is very good they facilitate staff nurses if you want any leave or want to change shifts.

Effective leaders in the healthcare industry must possess emotional intelligence in order to inspire their teams, forge close bonds with others, and handle challenging circumstances with compassion and understanding.

Better patient outcomes and a happier workplace are likely to result from nurses feeling encouraged, supported, and involved in their work under emotionally savvy leaders. It has been found that behaviors or supervisors towards nurses is quite good that is a positive point for the nurses to stay motivated

Esteemed needs

Acknowledgement and Recognition:

Lack of appreciation for nurses' efforts might demotivate them, which will impair their morale and job satisfaction (Morvati, 2024). It may also increase turnover and burnout, which will ultimately affect patient care. Nurses' morale and job satisfaction can be severely damaged when they believe their efforts are not recognized or valued (Mohamed, 2024). Their general well-being and level of involvement at work may suffer as a result of feeling underappreciated and undervalued.

Yes I get appreciations from hospitals. Not everytime but I have received recognition and shields 2-3 times in my six years or clinical experience.

Lack of appreciation can make nurses feel disengaged and demotivated, which may raise turnover rates as they look for more rewarding and encouraging work settings. Burnout, a condition of emotional, physical, and mental tiredness, can also result from this, which can have a detrimental effect on the nurse's health as well as their capacity to deliver high-quality patient care. A supportive and upbeat work atmosphere depends on nurses' efforts being recognized and appreciated. A culture of gratitude, increased team morale, and increased job satisfaction can all be achieved via the implementation of meaningful recognition programs, which will eventually improve patient care and results.

Leadership opportunities

It's vital to recognize that career growth and promotion can occasionally be difficult. Workload, a lack of leadership opportunities, and the requirement for ongoing education are some of the issues that may have an impact on career progression (Bradford, 2024). Although some nurses want to be leaders, not all nurses will have easy access to management or administrative positions due to the competitive nature of the path (Kotp, 2025).

P1: yes there are leadership opportunities but No equal opportunity for staff nurses from the management in leadership roles. And newly appointed nurses have to suffer a lot.

Nurses frequently need to obtain additional education, certificates, and specialized training in order to progress in their careers, which can be expensive and time-consuming. It has been found that leadership show discrimination among staff nurses that can be a big trauma for nurses to grow in that environment a mentioned by the participant for new nurses there are few opportunities to lead and grow.

Self Actualization

Opportunities for growth

Professional development opportunities including leadership positions, mentoring, and continuing education greatly increase nurses' motivation and engagement, which improves patient care and retention (Kakyo, 2025). When they perceive a clear path for growth, nurses are more likely to be driven and dedicated to their job. Giving nurses access to professional development programs and continuing education courses enables them to grow professionally and acquire new skills.

P1: yes there are opportunities for growth if any staff takes initiative by itself to get higher education then facilitated by the organization in shifts (for six month) but we dont get motivation from the organization or authorities to get higher education.

Relevant career development programs

In addition to helping healthcare professionals plan tailored care for clients based on their developmental stage, growth and development theories offer a framework for understanding this vast array of changes and offer parents and caregivers proactive advice.

P1: Seminars were organized especially in covid at Agha Khan Hospital and still seminars are organised on different diseases but there is no sense of higher education dont get any motivation from higher authorities and the management to pursue further education no professional growth seminars for MSN or other opportunities

It has been found that there are opportunities for the staff nurses to grow as seminars are organized that keep staff nurses up to date towards latest knowledge and information about new emerging diseases. But

there is lack of motivation from the management to motivate staff nurses to get higher education that can be a leading cause towards lack of motivation towards professional growth

Conclusion

It has been discovered that staff nurses are not happy with their pay. Because they don't receive a significant amount of compensation despite working lengthy shifts, this makes nurses feel demotivated. They therefore make the decision to go abroad to nurse. Therefore, one of the reasons why staff nurses get demotivated is their pay. Workload, particularly during public holidays, and staffing shortages have been proven to demotivate staff nurses from pursuing their goals and pursuing higher education. It has been discovered that there are sufficient regulations to safeguard patients' physical and emotional health, but hospital staff members incite violence. Therefore, it is necessary to enhance this procedure and establish a secure workplace to encourage staff nurses to. Staff nurses have been found to lack collaboration. There are currently no established avenues for nurses to communicate with one another. In addition to their employment, nurses should have enjoyable activities to keep them interested in their workplace and inspired to continue growing. It has been discovered that supervisors' treatment of nurses is often positive, which helps the nurses maintain their motivation. It has been discovered that leadership displays discrimination among staff nurses, which can be a significant trauma for nurses to develop in that setting. The participant also noted that there aren't many opportunities for new nurses to lead and develop in that setting. It has been discovered that staff nurses have the opportunity to develop because seminars are held to keep them informed about the most recent developments in emerging diseases. However, the management's lack of enthusiasm to encourage staff nurses to pursue further education may be a major contributing factor to their lack of drive for career advancement.

Recommendation:

Nurses salaries need revision to escalate their motivation towards their professional growth.

Cheaper career opportunities should be provided to nurses.

Workload should be minimized to improve patient safety and care.

REFERENCES

- Abbas, S., Zakar, R., Fischer, F., & Gilani, A. (2022). Challenges perceived by nursing professionals in physician-centred organizations: an exploratory qualitative study. *International nursing review*, 69(3), 384-391.
- Akbari, K., Yari, A., & Ostadtaghizadeh, A. (2024). Nurses' experiences of providing medical services during the Kermanshah earthquake in Iran: a qualitative study. *BMC emergency medicine*, 24(1), 4.
- Akkuş, Y., Karacan, Y., Güney, R., & Kurt, B. (2022). Experiences of nurses working with COVID-19 patients: A qualitative study. *Journal of clinical nursing*, 31(9-10), 1243-1257.
- Aldabbas, H., Pinnington, A., Lahrech, A., & Blaique, L. (2025). Extrinsic rewards for employee creativity? The role of perceived organisational support, work engagement and intrinsic motivation. *International Journal of Innovation Science*, 17(2), 237-260.
- Ali, I., & Gir, J. (2025). WORK LOAD RELATED STRESS AMONG NURSES IN TERTIARY CARE HOSPITAL KARACHI PAKISTAN. *Journal of Medical & Health Sciences Review*, 2(1).
- Almeida, D., Figueiredo, A. R., & Lucas, P. (2024, January). Nurses' well-being at work in a hospital setting: a scoping review. In *Healthcare* (Vol. 12, No. 2, p. 173). MDPI.
- Alshalawi, S., Aljedaani, S., Fintyanh, D., Salim, S., Fairaq, W., & Refaei, S. (2025). The Effect of Nurse-Patient Communication on Patient Satisfaction in the Emergency Department. *J Nurs Midwifery Sci*, 12(1), e158740.
- Amarneh, B. (2024). *Mitigating Nurse Burnout Using Emotional Intelligence Training and Nurse Leader Rounding* (Doctoral dissertation, California Baptist University).

- Arogundade, A. M., & Akpa, V. O. (2023). Alderfer's Erg and McClelland's Acquired Needs Theories-Relevance in Today's Organization. *Scholars Journal of Economics, Business and Management*, 10(10), 232-239.
- Bradford, N., Kirk, D., Taylor, K., Williams, N., McErlean, G., Cook, O., ... & Moore, E. (2024, October). Cancer Nurses' Voices and Recommendations to Address Workforce Challenges: A Qualitative Analysis. In *Seminars in Oncology Nursing* (Vol. 40, No. 5, p. 151722). WB Saunders.
- Brubakk, K., Godfrey, M., Kwaku, F., Solberg, T., & Toure, Y. (2024). Can bilateral labour agreements safeguard the rights, health and well-being of internationally educated nurses in Europe? Full report & recommendations.
- Buheji, M., & Mushimiyimana, E. (2023). Raising Gaza survival capacity as per violence experienced lesson from best war survival stories in recent history. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Social Sciences and Humanities (IJARSSH)*, 7(1), 22-48.
- Bukhari, S. U. P., Ali, K. K., Ashiq, R., Rub, H. A. A., & Kalhoro, I. A. (2024). Leadership Qualities and the Socio-Emotional Well-being of Learners: A Case Study. *Qlantic Journal of Social Sciences*, 5(2), 232-240.
- Bukhari, S. U. P., Rafique, M., Raza, F., Iqbal, S., & Khan, D. A. (2024). Leadership Philosophies and Team Dynamics: A Qualitative Exploration of Lived Experiences of Educational Leaders in Karachi. *Qlantic Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities*, 5(2), 307-316.
- El-Gazar, H. E., Ali, A. M., Shower, M., Serag, R. M., & Zoromba, M. A. (2025). Decent work and nurses' work ability: A cross-sectional study of the mediating effects of perceived insider status and psychological well-being. *International Journal of Nursing Studies Advances*, 8, 100283.
- Fredericks, S., Sanders, J., Back, M., Desteghe, L., Gomes, A., Marques-Sule, E., ... & Hendriks, J. M. (2025). Nurses and allied professionals' engagement in clinical research-in-practice: a statement of the Association of Cardiovascular Nursing & Allied Professions of the European Society of Cardiology. *European Journal of Cardiovascular Nursing*, zvae172.
- Golzar, J., Noor, S., & Tajik, O. (2022). Convenience sampling. *International Journal of Education & Language Studies*, 1(2), 72-77.
- Hameed, S. (2024). Underappreciation of Nurses in Pakistan: A Silent Catalyst for Burnout. *NURSEARCHER (Journal of Nursing & Midwifery Sciences)*, 01-01.
- Hancock, D. R., Algozzine, B., & Lim, J. H. (2021). Doing case study research: A practical guide for beginning researchers.
- Haroon, M. Z., & Thaver, I. H. (2022). An assessment of existing surge capacity of tertiary healthcare system of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Province of Pakistan using workload indicators for staffing need method. *Human Resources for Health*, 19(Suppl 1), 120.
- Hsiao, Y. H., Chen, L. F., & Hsu, C. Y. (2022). DATA-DRIVEN APPROACH TO EXPLORE EMPLOYEES'JOB NEEDS: AN EMPIRICAL STUDY OF DEPARTMENT STORE CHAIN IN TAIWAN. *International Journal of Industrial Engineering*, 29(5).
- Jannah, Q. A., & Balties, S. (2024, September). Grit, Personality, And Job Burnout Among Indonesian Nurses. In *Proceedings of International Conference on Psychology, Mental Health, Religion, and Spirituality* (Vol. 2, No. 01, pp. 16-24).
- Juste, D. (2024). *The Leadership Role and Emotional Intelligence as Empathy: A Qualitative Study* (Doctoral dissertation, Capella University).
- Kakyo, T. A., Xiao, L. D., & Chamberlain, D. (2025). The role of motivation in the initiation and maintaining mentoring relationships among nurses and midwives. *International Nursing Review*, 72(1), e12977.

- Kotp, M. H., Aly, M. A., Ismail, H. A., Elmoaty, A. E. E. A., & Basyouny, H. A. A. (2025). Nursing graduates' perceived future career pathway and career shift tendency in Egypt: a cross sectional study. *BMC nursing*, 24(1), 190.
- Li, B. (2025). Unintended Consequences of Follow-Up Care: Patient Experiences with Hypertension Management in Chinese Community Nursing. *Journal of Community Health Nursing*, 1-16.
- Limungi, G. M., Amer, M., Elmadani, M., Simon, K., Hamad, O., Horvath, E., ... & Orsolya, M. (2025). Understanding Key Factors Contributing to Mental Health Challenges Among Paediatric Nurses: A Systematic Review. *Frontiers in Public Health*, 13, 1480024.
- Manning, A. (2021). The elusive employment effect of the minimum wage. *Journal of Economic Perspectives*, 35(1), 3-26.
- Maslow, Abraham H. 1943. "Theory of Human Motivation." *Psychological Review* 50:370-396
- Maslow, Abraham H., with Deborah C. Stephens, and Gary Heil. 1998. *Maslow on Management*. New York, NY: John Wiley.
- Mazzocca, C., Acar, A., Uluagac, S., Montanari, R., Bellavista, P., & Conti, M. (2025). A survey on decentralized identifiers and verifiable credentials. *IEEE Communications Surveys & Tutorials*.
- Mlambo, M., Silén, C., & McGrath, C. (2021). Lifelong learning and nurses' continuing professional development, a metasynthesis of the literature. *BMC nursing*, 20, 1-13.
- Mohamed, S. A. A. K., & Shaban, M. (2024). Age and expertise: The effects of ageism on professional recognition for senior nurses. *Geriatric Nursing*, 60, 70-78.
- Morrow, E., Lynch, M., & Kearns, T. (2025). Non-clinical employment as an indicator of language proficiency in nursing and midwifery: a review of regulators' policies and international evidence.
- Morvati, D., Solbakken, R., Vaag, J. R., & Hilli, Y. (2024). Nurse Leaders' Motivational Forces in Developing a Health-Promoting Work Environment: A Hermeneutic Study. *Journal of Nursing Management*, 2024(1), 3040594.
- Nagel, C., Lindstrom, P. N., Westergren, A., Persson, S. S., & Nilsson, K. (2025). Nurses' health and work experiences during the COVID-19 pandemic in Swedish prehospital and hospital care: a deductive content analysis through the lens of the swAge model. *BMC Public Health*, 25(1), 304.
- Naz, S., Majeed, S., Bukhari, J. S., & Basheer, N. (2024). Factor influencing migration and job satisfaction amongst pakistani nurses: a study of pushing and pulling factors in multan institute of cardiology and nishtar hospital multan. *Biological & Clinical Sciences Research Journal*, 2024(1), 1453. <https://doi.org/10.54112/bcsrj.v2024i1.1453>
- Olorunyomi, T. D., Sanyaolu, T. O., Adeleke, A. G., & Okeke, I. C. (2024). Integrating FinOps in healthcare for optimized financial efficiency and enhanced care. *International Journal of Frontiers in Science and Technology Research*, 7(2), 20-28.
- Patrician, P. A., Bakerjian, D., Billings, R., Chenot, T., Hooper, V., Johnson, C. S., & Sables-Baus, S. (2022). Nurse well-being: A concept analysis. *Nursing Outlook*, 70(4), 639-650.
- Phuong Hong, N. T., & Tra My, P. T. (2024). Effects of financial characteristics on accounting conservatism of listed companies in Vietnam stock exchange. *Cogent Business & Management*, 11(1), 2289199.
- Rahman, J. ur, Ahmed, H., Bibi, M., & Kaukab, S. R. (2024). Exploring the Relationship between Job Satisfaction and Professionalism among Nurses in Karachi Pakistan. *Social Science Review Archives*, 2(2), 1615-1626. <https://doi.org/10.70670/sra.v2i2.217>
- Sultana, S. (2024). Barriers and Facilitator Factors to Career Advancement in Nursing Profession of Bangladesh.

- Thompson, M. A. D. D. Y. (2022). The Ethical Recruitment of Internationally Educated Nurses? An Examination of the Devaluing of Nursing in the Philippines, a Sending Region. *From Global Migration, Gender, and Health Professional Credentials: Transnational Value Transfers and Losses*, 187-208.
- Waris, S. H., Bashir, M., Imtiaz, M., Tasneem, S., & Jabeen, R. (2024). Factors affecting job motivation among nurses of a tertiary care hospital of lahore. *Biological & Clinical Sciences Research Journal*, 2024(1), 1332. <https://doi.org/10.54112/bcsrj.v2024i1.1332>
- Wiedermann, C. J., Barbieri, V., Engl, A., & Piccoliori, G. (2024). Impact of relational coordination on job satisfaction and willingness to stay: a cross-sectional survey of Healthcare professionals in South Tyrol, Italy. *Behavioral Sciences*, 14(5), 397.
- Wu, J., Song, J., Zhang, M., Li, L., & Shen, Q. (2025). The intermediary effect of work stress on the relationship between off-duty professional growth and reflective ability among mid-and senior-level nurses. *BMC nursing*, 24(1), 62.

